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FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH GRIT LEVEL AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS IN GIPORLOS NATIONAL TRADE SCHOOL – A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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CHAPTER I INTRODUCTION

Public school teachers play a pivotal role in shaping the academic and personal development of students, and their effectiveness is closely tied to individual traits such as grit. However, despite the acknowledged importance of grit levels of public schools' teachers, particularly within the context of Giporlos Trade National High School.

The existing literature highlights the challenges faced by educators in public schools, including high workloads, limited resources, and sometimes inadequate support systems (Ingersoll & Strong, 2011). This prompts the need to explore how these factors, along with individual characteristics and professional experiences, contribute to or hinder the development of grit among teachers at Giporlos Trade National High School.

(Duckworth, A., 2016) defines grit as the combination of passion and perseverance over the long term, highlighting its relevance to sustained achievement in challenging endeavors. Research by Rimm-Kaufman, S.E., and Hamre B. K. (2010) underscores the learning environment. This study builds upon the determinants of grit among public school teachers, recognizing that individual traits and external factors may shape the grit levels within this unique context.

Furthermore, the challenges faced by educators in public schools have been extensively documented Ingersoll & Strong (2011). This research aligns with these findings and aims to uncover how factors such as workload, support systems, and professional development opportunities contribute to or detract from the grit levels of teachers at Giporlos Trade National High School.

People with high levels of grit (also known as "gritty") maintain effort and eagerness to achieve their goals even when faced with significant obstacles Duckworth, A. L., Peterson, C., Matthews, M. D., & Kelly, D. R. (2007). In this context, a validated, self-administered/ reported survey has been developed to assess grit through a predefined scale known as the "Short Grit Scale, Grit-S". This

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scale indicates the positive outcomes independent of intelligence predictors among different individuals (Duckworth et al., 2007). Several studies have reported the success of the grit scale in measuring predictors that affect teachers' outcomes (Duckworth et al., 2009; Maddi et al., 2012)

In the field of education, the focus on student well-being and academic achievement often overshadows the importance of teachers' happiness. It has been noticed that when a person is happy and contented, they get most of their lives and become successful. It is claimed that people who are always striving towards their long-term goals keep you motivated, happy, and pleased, because if they weren't satisfied or happy, they will not work persistently to reach their long-term goals.

This study linked public-school teachers' grit to their level of happiness and demographic profile. This study will serve as the foundation for future research into grit as a predictor of success.

Statement of the Problem

Public school teachers play pivotal role in shaping the educational landscape, yet there is a gap in understanding the specific determinants that influence their grit levels- defined as the combination of passion and perseverance- in the face of challenges and demands within the profession. This research seeks to address the following key questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age
 - 1.2 sex
 - 1.3 civil status
 - 1.4 Teaching experience (Years)
 - 1.5 Workloads
 - 1.6 Educational Background
 - 1.7 Socioeconomic Status
2. What is the respondent's level of happiness?
3. What is the grit level of the respondent?
4. Is there a significant between the respondents' demographic profile and the level of grit?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of happiness and their level of grit?

Significance of the Study

The significance of the study on the determinants influencing grit levels among public school teachers lies in the potential to contribute valuable insights and benefits to various stakeholders within the educational landscape.

To DepEd, the findings could use the study's insights to design and implement tailored professional development programs. These programs can lead to targeted strategies for enhancing teacher commitment and resilience.

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To School Administrators, Insights into factors influencing grit levels can contribute to initiatives aimed at enhancing faculty well-being. Schools can implement strategies to reduce stress, improve job satisfaction, and create a positive work environment.

To Future Researchers, future studies may complement the quantitative findings with qualitative exploration. In-depth interviews or focus groups can provide a richer understanding of teachers' experiences, shedding light on the subjective aspects of grit.

Scope of the Study

The study will focus on public school teachers within the school of Giporlos Trade National High School, encompassing different educational levels. It utilizes a quantitative approach, collecting data through surveys and standardized instruments, and will consider demographic variables such as age, gender, years of teaching experience, educational background, and socioeconomic status.

The finding may have a limited generalizability beyond the specific geographic focus. Self-report measures may introduce response bias, and cross-sectional design provides a snapshot rather than a longitudinal view. The study's quantitative approach may not fully capture qualitative insights into teachers' experiences, and external factors are beyond the study's scope. Additionally, individual differences among teachers and resources constraints may impact the study's breadth and depth.

Definition of Terms

Grit-is defined as the combination of passion and perseverance towards long-term goals, as measured by the Grit Scale developed by Angela Duckworth.

Happiness- Along lasting state of mind that includes not only sentiments of joy, happiness, and other pleasant emotions, but also a sense that one's life is worthwhile and valued.

Public School Teachers- refer to educators employed by government funded educational institutions that provide primary, secondary, or higher education to general public.

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CHAPTER II REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter discusses the nature independent variables, dependent variables and how they are possibly associated as mentioned through some previous researches.

The Background of Grit

It is interesting to know the term that keep the teachers persevere in pursuing a long-term objective that is full of challenges and interests. Angela Duckworth has been a focal point in the field of psychology and achievement studies. Grit is described as the mix of desire and tenacity in achieving long-term goals. Rather than concentrating merely on skill or intellect, Duckworth's study highlights the importance of perseverance and resilience in attaining success.

Further research on grit has looked at its use in a variety of contexts, including grit in the workplace, grit in sports, and grit across diverse demographics. Researchers have also looked into potential therapies to help people develop grit and tenacity.

Research on the determinants of grit levels among public school teachers is crucial for understanding the elements that contribute to their tenacity and performance in difficult educational settings. (Tria, Jose, 2023) discovered a link between job happiness and grit levels among teachers, indicating that content and satisfied educators may have greater levels of persistence. A study conducted by Johnson et al. (2018) found that supportive leadership was connected with improved resilience and determination in addressing professional obstacles; it also investigated the influence of workload on grit among teachers.

According to the study, teachers who saw their workload as manageable were more likely to exhibit higher levels of persistence (Guimary, Faith & Gabunilas, Lowell & Gonzales, Merlyn, 2022). Agrawal, Chukkali, (2022) and Singh conducted a study on professional growth investigated the link between engagement in continual professional growth and grit. Teachers who participated in continuous opportunities demonstrated higher grit. Furthermore, it investigates the relationship between positive student-teacher interactions and grit. Teachers who reported excellent ties with their pupils displayed more tenacity (Fabelico, Fitzgerald & Afalla, Bonimar, 2020).

Ryan, Richard, and Deci, Edward (2020) Intrinsic motivation plays an important influence on the teacher's grit proposed that instructors motivated by a true love for teaching were more likely to demonstrate perseverance and resilience. Research conducted by S. Yahya Hejazi and Majid Sadoughi (2023) investigated the effect of organizational support systems on grit levels. Teachers who reported significant support from their educational institutions displayed more tenacity. Teachers' coping mechanisms play a significant role in why some of them remain in their jobs. Honra. Joelash. (2022) investigated the coping techniques used by teachers in stressful situations and their relationship to grit.

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Effective coping mechanisms were connected with higher levels of determination. With grit being proposed as a necessary trait for academic success, evaluating teacher's capacity to persist despite setbacks is critical. Therefore, grit can be a crucial driver for teachers' achievement and success, even when controlling for factors like a teacher's ordinary intelligence. Unfortunately, there is a lack of comprehensive data on which to base an evaluation of grit among Giporlos Trade National High School teacher population. Therefore, this study aimed to assess the level of grit among public school teachers of Giporlos Trade National High School.

Demographic profile and its association with grit

Dobbins (2016) did a correlational analysis in terms of correlational research.

This demonstrates that there is a statistically significant association between instructor grit and student achievement as well as instructor effectiveness. Individuals, according to Argon and Kaya (2018), people with stronger grit are more devoted to their aims and accomplish better than others. Others have a lower grit, Suzuki and co. (2015) and Robinson (2015) discovered a link. However, Suzuki et al. (2015) found a link between their demographic profile and their grit discovered no relation. The researcher hypothesized that there is a link and that it is significant in this investigation. The association between the faculty's demographic profile and their grit level. In terms of correlation and predictive function, members are ranked first. As a result of this, the researcher evaluates if the faculty's demographic profile can predict their level of grit and grit is a deciding element in academic employment retention.

Happiness associated with grit

Life fulfillment and happiness are intimately related to grit in how someone responds to life. Surprisingly, Joyance Partners (2022) discovered this in a research, people who set objectives and work hard to achieve them are often happy and content with their life because they are academically successful, paving the path for a rich future.

Theoretical Framework

Grit theory is based on perseverance theory. Perseverance refers to our motivational resolve to accomplish the action. To achieve a goal, one must be motivated, recognize the role that one's values play in goal setting, exercise persistence to overcome hurdles, and be determined to attain the goals.

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Conceptual Framework

The dependent variable in determining the grit level of public-school teachers is the primary objective of this study. The respondents' personal profiles, as well as their degree of happiness, will be assessed by the grit of public-school educators. The study's schema is illustrated in the picture below:

Figure 1. *Schema of study*

Statement of Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and the level of grit.
2. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' possible risk factors and their level of grit.

CHAPTER III METHODOLOGY

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Figure 2. The locale Map of the Study

Respondents of the Study

The study's respondents are public-school teachers currently working at Giporlos Trade National High School.

Sampling Technique

This research will use stratified random sampling to ensure that all GNTS teachers have an equal opportunity to participate. The researchers will obtain every multiple of three names from the official list of hired educators. Respondent will be included if they are formally employed on the Giporlos Trade National High School campus and willing to participate in this study. Exclusion criteria will be the teachers that are not willing to be a respondent.

Data Collection

Data for this study will be collected once the researchers have received approval from their Course Professor. A formal letter will be issued to the faculty of Giporlos Trade National High School, addressed to the School Head, seeking permission to collect data from faculty as well as a list of officially hired teachers in various departments. The replies will then be chosen methodically. After selecting possible respondents, researchers would approach them and invite them to engage in answering the study questionnaire of their own will.

Data Analysis

After the data has been organized, coded, and encoded in Excel, it will be evaluated using provided statistical tools. Measures of Central Tendency will be used to compute the Mean, percentage, and frequency for objectives 1, 2, and 3. The standard deviation will also be computed to determine the variability of the demographic variable's data.

This study incorporates inferential statistics, which will be used on Objectives 4, 5, and 6. Pearson r between numerical variables, Spearman ρ between ordinal variables, and Kendall Tau between numerical and categorical variables will be used to compute significant connections.

Ethical Considerations

Each respondent will be provided a consent form before the collection of data begins, along with the research instrument. The participants' signatures will be attached to the authorization form page to ensure that they participate voluntarily.

All data obtained will be kept strictly concealed, according to ethics norms and regulations.

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CHAPTER IV RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents demographic profile

The teachers' demographic profile was made with various array of items like teachers' age, sex, civil status, educational background, length of service in teaching, workloads and socioeconomic status.

Table 1 the demographic variables of the respondents with its corresponding frequency and percentage. There are 54.9% teachers who participated have age range of 35 years old and above with the mean of 39.29. Many of the public-school teacher pursue graduate studies as soon as they got hired in public-school because in this study 62.7% percent are having Maters Units whose age are between 32 and above years old. There are 68.6% percent female more than male who participated in the study.

Furthermore, table 1 reveals that 56.9% of teachers who completely finished their master's degree. They are motivated to enroll graduate school not just to acquire new skills or to have an advanced technical understanding of their fields but also in the reason that many benefits are awaits on them like job promotion and other incentives.

In this study about 47.1% percent public school teachers whose length of service have range from one to five years. Approximately, there are 28 public school teachers who have 1 to 2 teaching workloads with an average of 54.9%. There's a huge number of public-school teachers who are in a middle class with a 94.1%.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the respondents, n = 51

Demographic Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
25 & below -	1	1.9
26- 28 -	11	21.6
29- 31 -	5	9.8
32- 34 -	5	9.8
35 & above -	28	54.9
Mean		39.29
Sex		
Male -	16	31.4
Female -	35	68.6
Civil Status		
Single -	22	43.1
Married -	29	56.9
Separated -	0	0

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Education		
Bachelors -	19	37.2
Masters -	32	62.7
Doctoral -	0	0
Teaching Experience		
1-5 -	24	47.1
6-10 -	11	21.6
11-15 -	6	11.8
16-20 -	3	5.9
21-25 -	3	5.9
26 & above -	4	7.8
Workloads		
1-2 -	28	54.9
3-4 -	17	33.3
5 & above -	6	11.8
Socioeconomic Status		
Lower -	3	5.9
Middle -	48	94.1
Upper -	0	0

Table 2. Level of Grit of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
somewhat gritty	5	9.8	9.8	9.8
slightly gritty	4	7.8	7.8	17.6
moderately gritty	10	19.6	19.6	37.2
extremely gritty	32	62.8	62.8	100
Total	51	100.0	100.0	
GRAND MODE			5	EXTREMELY GRITTY

Table 2 displays the grit level of public-school teachers. The modal value is 5, which the scale's developer describes as "extremely gritty." Duckworth coined the term "grit" in 2007, after concluding in her research that the more the grit, the higher the degree of contentment among professionals. The term "grit" refers to the effort and tenacity required to attain long-term goals in life. It demonstrates that people are persistent and work hard to achieve these goals. The public-school educators of Giporlos National Trade School have a high grit level, indicating that they are determined to attain their goals.

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Table 3. Level of Happiness of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
somewhat unhappy	6	11.8	11.8	11.8
Not particularly happy	14	27.4	27.4	39.2
or unhappy				
Somewhat happy	16	31.4	31.4	70.6
or moderately happy				
very happy	10	19.6	19.6	90.2
too happy	5	9.8	9.8	100
GRAND MODE			4	SOMEWHAT HAPPY

Table 3 illustrates the level of happiness among public school teachers. The grand mode is 4, which the creator of the scale interprets as "somewhat happy"; 16 among 51 respondents described themselves as moderately happy. The level of happiness varies according to specific life domains. Happier is better in relationships or in intermediate levels of happiness, such as wealth, education, and political involvement.

While certain educators complain about their workloads, compensation, and educational progress, others find it demanding, but it also provides them with hope and happiness. Participation in school activities, receiving excellence, student appreciation, and social interactions are some of the school experiences that teachers cherish throughout their professional lives.

Table 4. Correlation table between respondents' demographic profile and their grit level.

IV	DV	Measure	Interpretation	P-Value	Interpretation	Decision
Demographic Grit						
Profile	level					
Age		-.034	No relationship	.812	Not significant	Accept Ho
Sex		-.314	No relationship	.025	Not significant	Accept Ho
Civil Status		.015	No relationship	.195	Not significant	Accept Ho
Education		-.128	No relationship	.369	Not significant	Accept Ho
Teaching Experience		.126	Weak	.380	Not significant	Accept Ho
Workloads		-.234	No relationship	.099	Not significant	Accept Ho
Socio						

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economic
Status .122 Weak .395 Not significant Accept Ho

Table 4 depicts the relationship between the demographic profile and grit level of public-school teachers. People's activities show a variety of interpretations based on their socio-demographic status. Correlations between demographic characteristics and grit levels can shed light on how age, gender, socioeconomic situation, and cultural background influence people's tenacity and passion for long-term goals.

All of the researched personal information about respondents' demographic profile, such as age, gender, civil status, educational attainment, year of teaching experience, workloads, and socioeconomic status, show no significant link with their grit level. As a result, the researchers accepted the null hypothesis, which states that there are no significant connections between respondents' demographic profiles and grit levels.

Table 5. Correlation table between respondents' happiness and their Grit

IV	DV	Measure	Interpretation	P-Value	Interpretation	Decision
Happiness	Grit	.441	Moderate	.001	Significant	Reject Ho

Table 5 was analyzed using Pearson's correlation to determine if grit is associated with happiness among public school teachers, who displayed a high level of grit. The correlation coefficient was 0.441 with a p-value < 0.001. Thus, it concluded that Happiness and Grit have a moderately positive association.

Duckworth, the originator of the grit scale, claims that the higher an individual's grit level, the greater their contentment or satisfaction. The teachers prove in this study that Duckworth's hypothesis is correct by finding a substantial association between respondents' levels of happiness and their grit level, as seen in Table 5. This supports the premise that when people are happy, they have an array of grit. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted: there is a strong association between respondents' levels of happiness and grit.

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CHAPTER V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

The study was done at Giporlos National Trade School, where public-school teachers participated during the School Year 2023-2024. The study aimed to determine the following: (1) the demographic profile of teachers in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational background, teaching experience, workloads, and socioeconomic status; (2) the level of grit of the teachers; (3) the level of happiness of the teachers; (4) the relationship between the teachers' demographic profile and their level of grit; and (5) the relationship between teachers' happiness and their grit. Data is gathered using descriptive statistical tools such as percentages, mean values, Pearson's correlation, and Spearman correlation.

The results of the study showed the following teachers' demographic profile. There are 54.9% of teachers have ages within range of 35 and above years old; here are more female teachers (68.6%) than male teachers (31.4%); Most of the teachers are married 56.9% than single 43.1% are participated; 62.7% of the teachers are pursuing their master's degree program; 47.1% of the teachers have served teaching for a period between 1 to 5 years; working load of the teachers are at the range between 1 to 2 preparation; and lastly 94.1% of teachers are in the middle class of person's position in the economic and social factors or the income level.

The Public-school teachers' level of grit is 5 which is interpreted as "extremely gritty".

The Public-school teachers' level of happiness is 4 which is interpreted according to the developer of the scale as "somewhat happy".

Findings showed that there was no significant relationship between the public-school teachers' demographic profile like age, sex, civil status, educational background, teaching experience, workloads and socioeconomic status and their grit level. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted that there is no significant relationship between teachers' demographic profile and their grit level.

This study found out that the theory of Duckworth is true that when happiness level of people is high, then there is a tendency that their grit level is also high.

Conclusion

This study on Factors Associated with Grit Level Among Public-School Teachers in Giporlos National Trade School - A Correlational Study was an excellent educational experience for us. In accordance with statistical evidence, teachers with a high degree of grit also have a high level of happiness; hence, grit has a beneficial impact on happiness. Pearson's correlation data support the

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final statement. The P value of .001 and the r value of .441 indicate that there is a moderately favorable link between grit and happiness among educators. As a result, the study's findings indicate that the higher the level of grit, the happier the teachers are.

Recommendation

The sample size can be expanded. For example, a sample of 100 respondents was employed; future studies may use a larger sample size. Furthermore, whereas this research is only conducted at Giporlos National Trade School in Giporlos, Eastern Samar, it may be undertaken on people from other locations. We also urge that future researchers perform longitudinal studies to examine changes in grit and happiness over time and assess the efficacy of interventions aimed at improving teacher resilience and well-being.

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